

A screenshot of the Zenodo website showing search results for the year 2018. The search bar contains "2018" and the results show two items: "Workflow Trace Archive alibaba2018 trace" (July 2, 2019) and "Abstracts' Book Special Issue SISA 2018" (November 6, 2018). Both items are marked as "Open Access". The interface includes filters for "Access Right" (Open, Closed, Restricted, Embargoed) and "Type".

List of OHEJP Publications 2018

The One Health EJP is a landmark partnership between partners across Europe, aligning and integrating medical, veterinary and environmental scientific communities to address potential and existing risks that originate at the animal-human-environmental interface.

All our project outcomes from the 5 year programme are available to view in yearly publication lists and via our [website](#).

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Role of systemic infection, cross contaminations and super-shedders in *Salmonella* carrier state in chicken.

Menanteau, P. Kempf, F., Trottereau, J., Virlogeux-Payant, I., Gitton, E., Dalifard, J., Gabriel, I., Rychlik, I., Velge, P. (2018). *Environmental Microbiology*. 20 (9), 3246–3260.

Project: **MOMIR**

Non-Typhi, non-Paratyphi *Salmonella*-related hospitalisations in Spain: trends, clinical aspects, risk factors for worse prognosis and hospital costs.

Garrido-Esteba, M., Latasa, P., Ordóñez-León, G.Y. et al. (2018) *European Journal of Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Disease*.

ISSN: 1435-4373

Project: **NOVA**

Analysis of consumer food purchase data used for outbreak investigations, a review.

Møller Frederik T, Mølbak Kåre, Ethelberg Steen. (2018) *Euro Surveill*.

Project: **NOVA**

Population Genetic Structure of *Listeria monocytogenes* Strains Isolated From the Pig and Pork Production Chain in France.

Félix B, Feuerer C, Maillet A, Guillier L, Boscher E, Kerouanton A, Denis M, Roussel S. (2018). *Front. Microbiol*.

Project: **LISTADAPT**

Veterinarios y antibióticos: destinados a entenderse.

Moreno MA., Florez-Cuadrado D., Ugarte-Ruiz M. and Dominguez L. (2018). *Profesión Veterinaria*. Asis.

ISBN: 2253-7244. 2018.

Project: **MoMIR-PPC**

Antimicrobial Resistance in the Food Chain in the European Union.

Florez-Cuadrado D., Moreno MA., Ugarte-Ruiz M. and Dominguez L. (2018). *Advances in Food and Nutrition Research*. Elsevier.

ISBN: 9780128139776. 2018

Project: **MoMIR-PPC**

Role of systemic infection, cross contaminations and super-shedders in *Salmonella* carrier state in chicken.

Menanteau P, Kempf F, Trottereau J, Virlogeux-Payant I, Guitton E, Dalifard J, Gabriel I, Rychlik I, and Velge P. (2018). *Environmental Microbiology*.

Project: **MoMIR-PPC**

Identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella variicola* and related phylogroups by MALDI-TOF Mass Spectrometry.

Rodrigues C, Passet V, Rakotondrasoa A, Brisse S (2018). *Front. Microbiol*. 9:3000

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

All OHEJP Publications from the 5 year programme can be viewed at: onehealthjep.eu